

Delamination Toughening of Composites Using Different Types Of Tufting Materials

Presented by

Manatsawee(San) Limprapuwattana

PhD Candidate, **RMIT University**, Australia
E: manatsawee.lim@gmail.com

Supervisory Team:

Anil Ravindran¹, Chun Wang², Adrian Mouritz¹, Raj Ladani¹

¹ Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology (RMIT) University, Melbourne, Australia

² University of New South Wales (UNSW), Sydney, Australia

—
What's next...

Introduction – 3D Reinforced Composites

- Delamination from
 - Impact damage
 - Fatigue loading
 - Overloading
- Through the thickness thermal and electrical conductivity

Boeing 787 Dreamliner Stringer problem

Delamination damage on T-joint composites

<https://www.engineerlive.com/content/composites-aircraft-improve-performance-there-are-challenges>

Lightning strike damage

https://www.boeing.com/commercial/aeromagazine/articles/2012_q4/4/

Non-destructive testing (NDT) technique

<https://www.aerospacetestinginternational.com/features/introduction-to-non-destructive-testing.html>

<https://kirill-guevara.livejournal.com/117050.html>

Methodology – Tufted Composites

Tufted composites

- Access required on one side only
- Can be used with fibrous based material and metal filament
- Can be automated
- Flexible process parameters (Tufting direction, embedded length, embedded angle, pattern)

Methodology – Tufted Composites

Shape Memory Alloy (SMA) wires

- Made of Nickel(Ni) and Titanium(Ti)
- Thermal Activated Shape Memory Alloy (SMA) wires
- Unique properties for many applications
 - Strain gauge
 - Damage detection
 - Shape morphing
 - Self-healing
 - Damping

Results:

- **Structural and Mechanical properties improvement**
 - **Delamination resistance**
 - **Fatigue resistance**
- **Multifunctional Properties engendered**

Benchmarking against Conventional Tufting materials

- **Carbon and**
- **Kevlar**

Metal filament:

- **Copper filament**

Results and Discussions

Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness of
Aramid, Carbon, Copper and SMA Tufts

Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness

Tufted Composites

- 200 gsm Plain Woven Composites
- Tufting materials: Aramid, Carbon, Copper and SMA wire
- %Areal content of 0.30%
- Vacuum assisted resin infusion

Methodology

- **Mode I** Interlaminar Fracture toughness

(Double Cantilever Beam (DCB)) test – ASTM D5528

Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) test – ASTM D5528 standard

Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness

Control sample

- No tufts inside
- Steady state value of 0.42 kJ/m²

Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness

- Copper tufted sample**
- Steady state value of 0.63 kJ/m^2
 - +49% Improvement

Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness

Carbon tufted sample

- Steady state value of 2.86 kJ/m²
- ~ 9 folds improvement

Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness

SMA tufted sample

- Steady state value of 4.34 kJ/m²
- ~ 9 folds improvement
- Large bridging scale observed

Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness

Aramid tufted sample

- Steady state value of 7.96 kJ/m²
- ~ 18 folds improvement
- Highest improvement observed

Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness

Toughening Mechanism due to “Large scale-bridging zone”

- Increased required force to propagate the crack
- Depending on pull-out mechanism of the tuft type – SMA showing largest amount of pull out

Mode I Interlaminar Fracture Toughness

Finite Element Modelling

- Using spring element (built-in Abaqus feature) to represent tufts
- Modified spring law using traction load law as a guide

Results and Discussions

Delamination Crack Closure of SMA tufts using large(0.25 mm) and small (0.15 mm) SMA wires at different propagation length

Delamination Crack Closure of SMA Tufts

- Using environmental chamber on Instron 50.1 kN machine
- Sample was tufted with 0.15 and 0.25 mm SMA as tufts at 0.3% areal content
- SMA wire transition temperature: 80 °C
- DIC Was used
- Mode I delamination crack closure
 - Efficacy at different propagation lengths
 - Efficacy test at fixed propagation length (4 cycles test)

Delamination Crack Closure of SMA Tufts

Delamination Crack Closure of SMA Tufts

Crack Closure Mechanism

- Shape Memory Effect (SME) of the SMA wires as tufts
- Phase transformation of the NiTi thermal SMA wire
- Repeatable process
- Strain recovery limit at 6-8%

Publication

- W. Khor, A. R. Ravindran, F. Ciampa, R. B. Ladani, **M. Limprapuwattana**, P. Whitton, A.D. Foreman, C. Meeks, A. Steele, T. Cooper, A. Rider, A.P. Mouritz (2023), **“Improving The Damage Tolerance Of Composite T-Joints Using Shape Memory Alloy Tufts”**, Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing 2023: p.107474

Acknowledgement

- In memory of Distinguished Professor Adrian Mouritz
- Supervisory team
 - Dr Anil Ravindran,
 - Professor Chun Wang,
 - Dr Raj Ladani

Presented by

Manatsawee (San) Limprapuwattana

RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/sanlim/>

—
What's next...

